

Reading and Study Habits as predictors to academic achievement of Business Education students in University of Benin in Affiliation with Federal College of Education (Tech.), Lagos

Aribisala, Oluwadamilare Olufolarin^{1*}, Igweh, Ayokunle Ogonnaya²

¹ Entrepreneurship Education Department, School of Business Education, Federal College of Education (Technical), Akoka, Lagos, Nigeria

² Entrepreneurship Education Department, School of Business Education, Federal College of Education (Technical), Akoka, Lagos, Nigeria

* Corresponding author: Dare_aribisala@yahoo.com

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Abstract

Habit is a route a person does regularly. It cannot be altered. Reading habit is a mental attitude in readiness to comprehension and reading. Study habit is systematic ways of efficiently produces academic output. Reading and study habits are strong variables in producing academic outputs based on sound academic records which are strong pillars to future personality stands. Habits is a process depending on the nature of the society. Mastery of academic tasks reveals the results of reading and studying. The level of comprehension measures both reading and study habits. The population covered business education in the program. The study tested a hypothesis that reading habits on academic achievements is not significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) among respondents. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation used in the test showed that reading habits has a significant relationship with business education students' academic achievements ($r=0.023 < P=0.05$). Also, it found out differences in business education performances of students due to their sex value of the sig. (2 tailed) ($r=0.068 > P=0.05$) means the group means are not statistically significant different. It was concluded that adequate reading and studying habits are strong predictors towards academic achievements of Business Education students.

Keywords: Academic achievement, Business Education, Predictors, Reading Habits and Study Habits

1. Introduction

Academic achievement is the final produce of educational attempt and process (Aribisala, 2023). This can be achieved fully when all things are put in place and when adequate habits are instilled and cultivated on the students. Aribisala, O.O. (2023) opined that business education inculcates certain habits, skills, etiquettes, norms and values for employability and self-reliance purposes in a life of an individual. Business education encounters the business world in rural and urban areas that prepares and engages them with positive attitude and competence in business and about business. Business education provides skills and knowledge enabling learners to adequately handle sophisticated software's, office technologies and information management. The under listed are some of objectives of Business Education:

1. Providing special training on business activities phases.
2. Providing business leadership training.
3. Providing financial management of successful training.
4. Developing a mature understanding of general nature of environment in business.

Awual (2015) defined business education as a system that trains and encourages beneficiaries acquire skills that makes them fit into the place of work. It encourages skills, attitudes and knowledge needed by citizens be effective in managing business in an economic system. Consequently, business education provides individual with adequate and vocational skills and better knowledge. It equips one with pedagogical ethics in education for and about business. Also, it is a programme of instructions equipping one with vocational competencies providing information about business (Osuala, 2004). FRN (2013) stated that it is an aspect of education leading to acquire applied and practical

knowledge in business. Aribisala (2021) stated that the achievement of a learner in academic endeavor solely depends on the level of how proficient the language of education is structured by the instructor.

Aribisala (2021) stated that the achievement of a learner in academic endeavor solely depends on the level of how proficient the language of education is structured by the instructor. Students' achievement needs adequate innovative techniques with more resilient evaluations (Aribisala, 2023). Igweh (2023) stated that it brings masters of goals and objectives of academic tasks. Development of exceptional performance in lessons enhances process of learning and boosts outcomes academically (Whitten, Labby and Sullivan, 2016). Aribisala (2023) opined that academic achievement is opined as an educational declaration of knowledge which covers students' intelligent domain on learning outcomes. Reading habits plays a very key role in enabling students in achieving efficient practical and theory skills in life. Reading activity is measured by measuring frequency of reading and comprehension. Reading is a major role in the learning process. It acquires knowledge for grading personally and developing one's knowledge base. Akande and Samson (2007) stated the ability to read brings the heart of educating oneself and lifelong transforming art is life and society. According to Chettri and Rout (2013) defined reading habit as materials

Mark and Howard (2019) opined that challenges faced by students is created due to ineffective study habits. According to Crede and Kunneel (2008), study habits is a study route, including self-test, adequate study sessions, learning and study in a conducive environment. It is the degree to which students regularly engages in appropriate reading patterns. Study habits refers to series of activities accepted by learners in the learning process of educating learning. It elicits responses regards cognitive procedures in the learning process. Study habits involves the following enlisted procedures

such as highlighting, note taking, summarizing and outlining to ensure adequate explicit instruction (Gettinger and Seibat, 2013). Harper and Row (2019) mentioned the following as attitude of students study habits:

1. Studying daily.
2. Creating a quiet conducive environment anywhere to study.
3. Studying in a technique suiting your learning style.
4. Avoiding all appliances disturbing when studying.
5. Taking regular breaks.
6. Avoiding late minute reading.
7. Asking for assistance if finding reading difficult.

The criteria in judging academic achievements brings potentialities and capabilities frequently measured by examination results and to pass judgements on quality of education by academic institutions. The present-day civilization emerged through continual transformation and evolution over the past centuries. Evidently, the crux of notable changes recorded in education. Education a process and an activity bringing the society aims and methods on the nature of the society it is used (Akeredolu, 2019). The education concerns economically have led to many studies aiming at identifying the predictors of students' academic performance (Stanca, 2018). Preparation and learning strategies employed consciously by students, goes a long way to influence their level of academic achievement (Ebele and Olofu, 2017). Study habits are ways students systematically in being more efficient or inefficient in academics (Ayodele and Adebisi, 2015)

2. Statement of the Problem

The ease of excelling as a student solely depends on reading habits and study habits to a large extent. The utilization of these two aforementioned increases higher academic achievement. Study habits is instrumental to the achievement of every business education student. Likewise, reading habit is a determinant of academic achievement. Business education students needs both habits to ensure adequate standards in the teaching learning process. On this basis, the major concern of this paper is to look into reading habits and study habits as predictors to academic achievement of Business Education students in University of Benin in Affiliation with Federal College of Education (Technical), Akoka, Lagos, Nigeria.

3. Purpose of the study

This study sets out to achieve the following objectives:

1. Examining the reading habits on academic achievements of business education students.
2. Identifying study habits as a predictors on academic achievement of business education students.
3. Determining the relationship between reading habits and study habits on academic achievement of business education students.

4. Research Questions

The following research questions will guide the study:

1. To what extent does reading habits affect academic achievements of business education students?
2. How does study habits acts as a predictors on academic achievement of business education students?

3. What is the relationship between reading habits and study habits on academic achievement of business education students?

University of Benin in Affiliation with Federal College of Education (Technical), Akoka, Lagos. Simple random sampling technique was used in selecting two hundred (200) students in obtaining revealing and frank responses.

5. Research Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis will be tested:

1. Reading habits on academic achievements of business education students is not significant.
2. Study habits is not a significant predictors to business education students' academic achievements.
3. There is no significant relationship between reading habits and study habits on academic achievements of business education students.

6. Methodology

The research utilized a descriptive survey. The hypotheses were formulated. Three hypothesis for this study. The instrument used for data collection in this research was questionnaire. The population used for this study are business education students in

7. Presentation of Results, Data

Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

HO1:

The null hypothesis was tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and the result is presented on Table 1.

Table 1: Reading Habits on academic achievements of Business Education students is not significant.

Table 1

Reading Habits on academic achievements of Business Education students

Correlations

		TOTAL READING HABITS	ACHIEVEMENT
TOTAL READING HABITS	Pearson Correlation	1	.023*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.043
	N	200	200
ACHIEVEMENT	Pearson Correlation	.023*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.043	
	N	200	200

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

From the analysis of table 1, it shows that Reading Habit has a significant relationship with business education students' academic achievements. This is because ($r = .023 < P = 0.05$). This answers the research question 1 which reads thus; 'To what extent does reading habits affect academic achievements of business education students? This implies that Reading Habit has a significant relationship with business education students' academic achievements.

Students that have good reading habit will have good achievements in business education courses.

Hypothesis 2: Study habits is not a significant predictors to business education students' academic achievements.

The null hypothesis was tested using an independent t-test

Table 2
Descriptive Statistics of Sex

Group Statistics					
	SEX	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
ACHIEVEMENT	MALE	86	13.3488	1.28124	.13816
	FEMALE	110	12.7091	3.02693	.28861

Table 3: Difference in Business Education Performance of Students due to their sex.

Table 3
Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
ACHIEVEMENT	Equal variances assumed	21.181	.000	1.835	194	.068	.63975	.34865	-.04789	1.32739
	Equal variances not assumed			1.999	154.292	.047	.63975	.31997	.00766	1.27184

The value in the sig-(2 tailed) row of 0.068 is greater than 0.05, so the group means are not statistically significantly different. There is no significant difference between Reading Habits and Academic Achievement of Business education Students due to gender. The hypothesis is accepted, because the means are not significantly different.

8. Discussion of Findings

The results of the findings show that in **Research Question 1**; to what extent does reading habits affect academic achievements of business education students? Is significant. This is so because, the r -cal $0.23 < \text{set } P = 0.05$. This shows that Students who have good reading habits perform well academically in Business education. This is in line with Horbec (2012) study which showed a strong relationship between reading habits and academic achievement. The reading habits significantly assists the students in their learning process and enhances their academic outcomes (Fatiloro, Oyekoa, & Hameed, 2017; Kidd & Castano, 2013; Whitten, Labby, & Sullivan, 2016). The point was buttressed further by Benevides and Peterson, (2010) who concluded that those who enjoyed reading had better scores.

Research Question 2; Reveals that How does study habits acts as a predictors on academic achievement of business education students male and female Business education Students. This is shown in t -call of $0.068 > \text{set } P = 0.05$ indicating that there is no gender significant difference in the reading habit and academic performance of Business Studies Students. This is in line with the Dilshad, Adnan and Akram (2013) investigated on gender differences in reading habits of university students and reported that reading habits of male and female students are somewhat different.

Buttressing the point further, Bas (2012) established through his findings that, reading habit of high school students showed a significant difference according to gender variable in favour of female students. Also, Abdu-Raheem (2012) in his study on gender differences and students' academic achievement reported that there was no significant

different between the achievement mean scores of male and female students' in the experimental and control groups. This is an indication that gender has no significant contribution to the achievement of student

9. Summary and Recommendations

This study has fully analyzed that reading and study habits as predictors to academic achievement of Business Education students of University of Benin in Affiliation with Federal College of Education (T), Akoka, Lagos. Also, it is concluded that reading habits and study habits are strong predictors to academic achievement of Business Education students. The comprehension, adaptability and understanding are key predictors towards reading and studying habits to academic achievements.

The following recommendations were given:

1. Adequate orientation should be given to the business education students and lecturers.
2. Lecturers and students of Business education should be given loads of assignment to boost their reading and study habits.
3. Coordination and organization of students for both habits should be strictly monitored.
4. Parents should inculcate both habits at the early stage.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization [A.O.O.; I. A. O.]; methodology [A.O.O.; I. A. O.]; validation [A.O.O.; I. A. O.]; formal analysis [A.O.O.; I. A. O.]; investigation [A.O.O.; I. A. O.]; resources [A.O.O.; I. A. O.]; data curation [A.O.O.; I. A. O.]; writing—original draft preparation [A.O.O.; I. A. O.]; writing—review and editing [A.O.O.; I. A. O.]; visualization [A.O.O.; I. A. O.]; supervision [A.O.O.; I. A. O.].

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Conflict of interest

The authors declares no conflict of interest

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